

Price Prediction for Airbnb Listings in New York

CSCI 724 – Survey of Ai

Bekalue Kobro

May 2024

North Dakota State University (NDSU)

Table of contents

LIST OF FIGURES	2
LIST OF TABLES	2
1. PROBLEM STATEMENT	3
2. IMPLEMENTATION STEPS	3
2.1 TOOLS, ENVIRONMENT SETUP, LIBRARIES AND DATASET	3
2.2 EXPLORATORY DATA ANALYSIS (EDA)	4
2.3 DATA CLEANING (PRE-PROCESSING)	7
2.3.1 Categorizing features	7
2.3.2 Handling Missing & Invalid Values	8
2.3.3 Handling Outliers (Extreme values)	8
2.3.4 Feature Selection	9
2.4 MODEL SELECTION, TRAINING AND EVALUATION	9
2.5 HYPERPARAMETER TUNING	11
3. SUMMARY OF RESULTS	12
4. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK	14
REFERENCES	15
APPENDIX – A: CODE FOR HANDLING MISSING VALUES	16
APPENDIX – B: CODE FOR HANDLING INVALID VALUES	17
APPENDIX – C: LINEAR REGRESSION CODE SNIPPET	18

List of Figures

<i>Figure 1: Project implementation steps</i>	3
<i>Figure 2: Top 20 neighborhoods in New York – few neighborhoods have higher number of listings.</i>	4
<i>Figure 3: Number of Airbnb listings in New York by room Type.</i>	5
<i>Figure 4: Box plot for price distribution among top 20 neighborhoods in New York</i>	5
<i>Figure 5: Price variation among various room types in New York.</i>	6
<i>Figure 6: Correlation Heatmap for features vs price of an Airbnb listing.</i>	6
<i>Figure 7: Bar-graph that shows correlation between features and price</i>	7
<i>Figure 8: Price range before and after removing extreme values</i>	9
<i>Figure 9: Performance before removing outliers (left) and after removing outliers (middle and right)</i>	10
<i>Figure 10: Performance of KNN vs SVR</i>	10
<i>Figure 11: performance of Random Forest vs Gradient Boost</i>	11
<i>Figure 12: Performance of gradient boosting with Hyperparameters</i>	12

List of Tables

<i>Table 1: Categories of features in the dataset</i>	7
<i>Table 2: Handling approaches for missing values and invalid values</i>	8
<i>Table 3: Descriptive summary of features that have numerical value.</i>	8
<i>Table 4: Summary of regression models' performance</i>	13

1. Problem statement

Predicting prices for Airbnb listings poses a significant challenge due to the dynamic nature of factors such as number of customers and location [1][2]. Traditional methods like Comparative Price Analysis or manual property appraisal often prove inefficient, failing to optimize revenue for hosts or provide competitive rates for guests. Therefore, there is a need for an automated pricing system that can accurately predict Airbnb rental prices. This would allow the host to accurately determine the return on investment (ROI) and provide a competitive pricing that would appeal for the guest.

To address this need, this project aims to leverage established machine learning algorithms to develop a predictive model for Airbnb rental prices. The methodology involves acquiring Airbnb listing data for New York, preprocessing the data, and employing popular machine learning regression models for price prediction.

Initial exploration of the dataset reveals the presence of outliers [3], extreme values in price ranges for Airbnb listings. Through careful handling of these outliers, various regression models were applied. Among the array of regression algorithms tested, the gradient boosting regression algorithm emerged as the most promising, exhibiting performance evaluation metrics of 33.49 on RMSE and 0.16 on R-squared. This result is consistent with results of related scholarly works [4].

2. Implementation steps

Figure 1: Project implementation steps

2.1 Tools, Environment Setup, Libraries and Dataset

Tools used in this project are mainly Jupiter notebook on Google Co-Lab as well as local machine. The source code is written in Jupiter notebook which is available via GitHub

repository¹. Choice of programming language is *Python 3.12.0* with all dependencies installed in a *Pipenv*² virtual environment. The list of required libraries are found in *Pipfile* and *pipfile.lock*³ with exact versions which can be used for deterministic builds. Some of Python libraries used are pandas data frame for processing data, matplotlib and plotly for visualizations, and sklearn for machine learning model training, testing and optimization.

The initial stages of the project started out with “New York City Airbnb Open Dataset⁴” (csv file) downloaded from Kaggle. Later, a better quality of dataset for New York city Airbnb listings has been acquired form OpenDataSoft⁵.

2.2 Exploratory Data Analysis (EDA)

Following the setup of a virtual environment and the acquisition of data, an exploratory analysis was conducted to unveil inherent patterns within the dataset. This preliminary analysis is aimed to identify areas requiring cleanup and preparation for AI model training.

Presented below are the insights gleaned from the initial data analysis:

1. *A minority of neighborhoods boast a disproportionately high number of Airbnb listings, despite the presence of 222 distinct neighborhoods as depicted in figure 1.*

Figure 2: Top 20 neighborhoods in New York – few neighborhoods have higher number of listings.

¹ https://github.com/BeTKH/airbnb_price_pred

² <https://pypi.org/project/pipenv/>

³ <https://stackoverflow.com/questions/46330327/how-are-pipfile-and-pipfile-lock-used>

⁴ <https://www.kaggle.com/datasets/dgomonov/new-york-city-airbnb-open-data>

⁵ <https://insideairbnb.com/new-york-city/>

2. Among four distinct room types, only home apartment and private room account for most of the room types in the dataset as shown in figure 2.

Figure 3: Number of Airbnb listings in New York by room Type.

3. The price range for listings has very high degree of variance in some neighborhoods (fig-3) and room types (fig-4) with some properties being priced less than \$100, while others being priced over \$10,000.

Figure 4: Box plot for price distribution among top 20 neighborhoods in New York

Figure 5: Price variation among various room types in New York.

4. Correlation heat map (figure-5) and the bar-plot (figure-6) shows the room price and the rest of the features in the dataset shows very weak correlation.

Figure 6: Correlation Heatmap for features vs price of an Airbnb listing.

Features and their Correlation with 'price'

Figure 7: Bar-graph that shows correlation between features and price

2.3 Data Cleaning (Pre-processing)

Through initial data analysis, it is evident that our dataset exhibits significant noise, characterized by extreme price ranges (outliers), crowding of listings in certain areas, and a lack of strong correlation between price and other features. These factors pose challenges for our AI-based price prediction model, hindering its ability to effectively learn and generalize from the data points to make predictions on unseen datapoints. To address this issue, we have conducted data cleaning and addressed outliers, as outlined below.

2.3.1 Categorizing features

As an initial phase in the data cleaning process, the first step undertaken was to classify the data features into appropriate categories, as outlined in the table below:

Table 1: Categories of features in the dataset

Feature Category	Column Labels (features)
<i>categorical</i>	'Neighbourhood', 'RoomType'
<i>Continuous (numerical)</i>	'RoomId', 'HostId', 'RoomType', 'MinimumNights', 'NumberOfReviews', 'NumberOfReviewsPerMonth', 'RoomsRentByTheHost', 'Availibility'
<i>text</i>	'Name'
<i>Date/Time</i>	'DateLastReview', 'UpdatedDate'
<i>Co-ordinates</i>	'Latitude', 'Longitude'

2.3.2 Handling Missing & Invalid Values

Missing values in the dataset were detected by aggregating the total occurrences of null values in each column of the data frame. A criterion established to flag erroneous entries for both numerical and continuous data is:

- Negative values within a continuous (numerical) list were deemed invalid,
- Geographic coordinates for New York falling outside the ranges of (40.5, 40.9) for latitude and (-74.25, -73.7) for longitude has also been considered as invalid.

The approach to handle missing values for categorical values is replacing missing values by the most common categorical value and all invalid values has been discarded from the record. The table below provides a summary of the procedure for handling missing and invalid entries.

Table 2: Handling approaches for missing values and invalid values

Feature category	fill Missing Values with:	Handle Invalid Values
Categorical	frequent Category	-
Continuous /numeric	Median	drop
Text Values	“Not Provided”	-
Date/Time	NaT	-

2.3.3 Handling Outliers (Extreme values)

The preliminary examination of the data also indicates a significant variance in the price range of Airbnb listings, characterized by extreme values. Specifically, the lowest and highest prices among the Airbnb listings are \$0.00 and \$10,000, respectively, as illustrated in the table below.

Table 3: Descriptive summary of features that have numerical value.

	MinimumNights	NumberOfReviews	NumberOfReviewsPerMonth	RoomsRentByTheHost	RoomPrice
count	48567.000000	48567.000000	48567.000000	48567.000000	48567.000000
mean	8.355282	23.261103	0.833166	5.919163	165.614121
std	22.366895	47.621105	1.164677	23.561705	454.134823
min	1.000000	0.000000	0.010000	1.000000	0.000000
25%	2.000000	1.000000	0.190000	1.000000	67.000000
50%	3.000000	4.000000	0.420000	1.000000	100.000000
75%	6.000000	22.000000	0.940000	2.000000	175.000000
max	1250.000000	746.000000	50.290000	261.000000	10000.000000

The presence of extreme values in the data contributes to additional noise in our dataset. To mitigate this, outliers are excluded from the training data for the AI model by setting the lower price limit to \$100 and upper price limit to \$250. The box plot below shows price variation in top 20 neighborhoods before and after removing the extreme values.

Figure 8: Price range before and after removing extreme values

However, the drawback of this approach is that it results in the loss of a substantial portion of data, consequently impacting the AI model's ability to effectively learn and generalize.

2.3.4 Feature Selection

Based on the insights from correlation matrix and co-relation bar plot, on figures 5 and 6 respectively, only features that have relatively strong correlation with price are selected as an input feature to predict price. Features excluded are those with least correlation such as longitude, number of reviews and number of reviews per month.

2.4 Model Selection, Training and Evaluation

Various machine learning regression algorithms has been used in related research works to predict price. The most used regression models in research papers are Linear regression, Logistic Regression, Random Forest, and Support Vector regression [4][5] [6]. Other regression models which are also applied to price prediction problem are Quantile Regression Analysis [7][8] and XGBoost [9].

For simplicity, linear regression model has been chosen for predicting price on the Airbnb listings. The model has been trained after data is split into 80% and 20% for training and for

testing respectively. Two iterations of training were executed using different versions of the dataset: one inclusive of outliers and the other with outliers removed.

The evaluation of the linear regression model's performance, measured by Mean Squared Error (MSE) and R-Squared, reveals a significant improvement in performance when outliers are excluded, as depicted in the graph below.

Figure 9: Performance before removing outliers (left) and after removing outliers (middle and right)

In addition to linear regression, K-nearest-neighbor, Support Vector regression, Random Forest And Gradient Boosting regression algorithms has also been trained and evaluated on clean dataset which uses price range between \$100 and \$250. The performance of each model is shown on the plots below:

Figure 10: Performance of KNN vs SVR

Figure 11: performance of Random Forest vs Gradient Boost

The results suggest that the gradient boosting regression model exhibits superior performance compared to other regression algorithms. Consequently, it has been selected as the preferred algorithm for further optimization.

2.5 Hyperparameter Tuning

To further optimize the algorithm, suitable values for hyperparameters must be chosen. The hyperparameters for gradient boost algorithm are explained below:

- Number of estimators: increasing number of estimators increases performance until certain point beyond which the training may lead to overfitting (*choice: $n_estimators = 140$*).
- Learning rate: controls the step size at each iteration. Lower values lead to more conservative boosting and better generalization (*choice: $learning_rate = 0.1$*).
- Maximum depth: increasing this value allows the model to capture more complex relationships in the data but also increases the risk of overfitting (*choice: $max_depth = 5$*).
- $min_samples_split$ and $min_samples_leaf$: control the minimum number of samples required to split an internal node or to be at a leaf node, respectively. Higher values can prevent overfitting (*choice: $min_samples_split = 2$ and $min_samples_leaf = 5$*).

- **Subsample:** This parameter specifies the fraction of samples to be used for fitting the individual base learners. Values less than 1.0 introduce stochasticity and can help prevent overfitting (*choice: `Subsample = 0.75`*).

Grid search was employed to pinpoint hyperparameter values conducive to accurate price prediction. Unfortunately, due to computational constraints and time limitations, optimal parameters could not be identified within a reasonable timeframe. Nevertheless, modest enhancements in prediction were observed through judiciously selected values.

Figure 12: Performance of gradient boosting with Hyperparameters

3. Summary of Results

Based on the evaluation of various regression models for Airbnb price prediction, the performance metrics indicate distinct strengths and weaknesses. The Linear Regression model exhibits a relatively higher Root Mean Squared Error (rMSE) of 61.074, accompanied by a modest R-squared value of +0.078, suggesting limited predictive accuracy. Conversely, the K-nearest-neighbor regression model demonstrates a notably lower rMSE of 37.358, although with a negative R-squared of -0.043, indicating poor fit to the data.

Both Random Forest and Gradient Boosting regression models show improved performance metrics, with rMSE values of 35.396 and 34.333, respectively, and positive R-squared values, suggesting better predictive capability.

Particularly, the Gradient Boosting regression model achieves the lowest RMSE of the evaluated models, alongside the highest R-squared value of +0.118, signifying superior predictive accuracy and model fit. The table below summarizes the results:

Table 4: Summary of regression models' performance

<i>Regression model</i>	RMSE (test)	R-squared (test)
<i>K-nearest-neighbor</i>	37.465	- 0.049
<i>Support Vector regression</i>	36.878	- 0.016
<i>Random forest</i>	35.170	+ 0.075
<i>Linear regression</i>	34.679	+ 0.101
<i>Gradient Boosting regression</i>	34.072	+ 0.132
<i>Gradient Boosting regression</i>^{*6}	33.498	+ 0.161

In summary, the findings indicate that Gradient Boosting regression stands out as the most promising algorithm for predicting Airbnb prices in New York. This conclusion aligns with similar outcomes observed in previous studies, including research utilizing the Boston Airbnb open dataset from Kaggle [4].

⁶ * - Gradient boosting with hyper-parameters

4. Conclusion and Future work

The analysis of Airbnb listings in New York revealed several challenges, including extreme price ranges and imbalanced categories. While efforts were made to mitigate these issues by excluding extreme price values, this approach led to a reduction in data points and hindered the effectiveness of regression models. Additionally, due to constraints, optimal parameters for Gradient Boost were not determined.

Future research should focus on identifying optimal hyperparameters and exploring a narrower scope, specifically focusing on the most common types of listings, such as home apartments and private rooms. Moreover, with access to a larger dataset, deep learning approaches could be explored. Furthermore, incorporating customer reviews through sentiment analysis could enhance predictive models and provide insights into future property prices.

References

- [1] Rezazadeh Kalehbasti, Pouya, Liubov Nikolenko, and Hoormazd Rezaei. "Airbnb price prediction using machine learning and sentiment analysis." In International Cross-Domain Conference for Machine Learning and Knowledge Extraction, pp. 173-184. Cham: Springer International Publishing, 2021.
- [2] McNeil, Brandon. "Price Prediction in the Sharing Economy: A Case Study with Airbnb data." (2020).
- [3] Wikipedia contributors, "Outlier," Wikipedia, The Free Encyclopedia, <https://en.wikipedia.org/w/index.php?title=Outlier&oldid=1181881199> (accessed May 5, 2024).
- [4] Wang, Haoqian. "Predicting Airbnb Listing Price with Different models." Highlights in Science, Engineering and Technology 47 (2023): 79-86.
- [5] Yu, Hujia, and Jiafu Wu. "Real estate price prediction with regression and classification." CS229 (machine learning) Final project reports (2016).
- [6] Rezazadeh Kalehbasti, Pouya, Liubov Nikolenko, and Hoormazd Rezaei. "Airbnb price prediction using machine learning and sentiment analysis." In International Cross-Domain Conference for Machine Learning and Knowledge Extraction, pp. 173-184. Cham: Springer International Publishing, 2021.
- [7] D. Wang and J. L. Nicolau, "Price determinants of sharing economy-based accommodation rental: A study of listings from 33 cities on airbnb. com," International Journal of Hospitality Management, vol. 62, pp. 120–131, 2017.
- [8] Pouya Rezazadeh Kalehbasti, Liubov Nikolenko, and Hoormazd Rezaei. Airbnb price prediction using machine learning and sentiment analysis. arXiv preprint arXiv:1907.12665, 2019.
- [9] Laura Lewis. Predicting airbnb prices with machine learning and deep learning, 2019.

Appendix – A: Code for Handling Missing values

```
# Function to fill missing values
def fill_missing_values(df):

    # Categorize columns
    categorical_cols = ['Neighbourhood', 'RoomType']
    continuous_cols = ['RoomId', 'HostId', 'RoomType', 'MinimumNights',
'NumberOfReviews',
'NumberOfReviewsPerMonth', 'RoomsRentByTheHost', 'Availability']
    text_cols = ['Name']
    dateTime = ['DateLastReview', 'UpdatedDate']

    #categorical values: replace missing values with the mode (most frequent value)
    for col in categorical_cols:
        if df[col].isnull().any():
            df[col].fillna(df[col].mode()[0], inplace=True)

    #continuous_cols:replace missing values with the median of each column.
    for col in continuous_cols:
        if df[col].isnull().any():
            df[col].fillna(df[col].median(), inplace=True)

    #For datetime:convert to datetime and NaT if not a time
    for col in dateTime:
        df[col] = pd.to_datetime(df[col], errors='coerce')

    #text columns: replace missing values with the string 'Not provided'
    for col in text_cols:
        df[col].fillna('Not provided', inplace=True)
    return df
```

Appendix – B: Code for Handling invalid values

```
def drop_invalid_geo(df):

    # Convert 'Latitude' and 'Longitude' columns to numeric
    df['Latitude'] = pd.to_numeric(df['Latitude'], errors='coerce')
    df['Longitude'] = pd.to_numeric(df['Longitude'], errors='coerce')

    # Define invalid geographic coordinate ranges for NYC
    min_latitude, max_latitude = 40.4774, 40.9
    min_longitude, max_longitude = -74.25, -73.7

    # Filter for valid geographic coordinates
    valid_geo_df = df[(df['Latitude'] >= min_latitude) & (df['Latitude'] <= max_latitude) &
                      (df['Longitude'] >= min_longitude) & (df['Longitude'] <= max_longitude)].copy()

    return valid_geo_df

def count_invalid_geo(df):

    # Convert to numeric
    df['Latitude'] = pd.to_numeric(df['Latitude'], errors='coerce')
    df['Longitude'] = pd.to_numeric(df['Longitude'], errors='coerce')

    # Define invalid geographic coordinate ranges for NYC
    min_latitude, max_latitude = 40.4774, 40.9
    min_longitude, max_longitude = -74.25, -73.7

    # Count entries with invalid geographic coordinates
    invalid_geo_count = ((df['Latitude'] < min_latitude) | (df['Latitude'] > max_latitude) |
                        (df['Longitude'] < min_longitude) | (df['Longitude'] > max_longitude)).sum()

    return invalid_geo_count
```

Appendix – C: Linear regression code snippet

```
import pandas as pd
from sklearn.model_selection import train_test_split
from sklearn.linear_model import LinearRegression
from sklearn.metrics import mean_squared_error, r2_score

# one-hot encoding for categorical variables
data_encoded = pd.get_dummies(data_selected, columns=['Neighbourhood', 'RoomType'],
drop_first=True)

# features (X) and target variable (y)
X = data_encoded.drop(columns=['RoomPrice'])
y = data_encoded['RoomPrice']

# Split the data
X_train, X_test, y_train, y_test = train_test_split(X, y, test_size=0.2, random_state=42)

# Initialize model, Train & predict

model = LinearRegression()
model.fit(X_train, y_train)
y_pred = model.predict(X_test)

# Evaluate performance
rmse = np.sqrt(mean_squared_error(y_test, y_pred))
r2 = r2_score(y_test, y_pred)

# Visualize
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt

# Plotting actual vs predicted values
plt.figure(figsize=(6, 6))
plt.scatter(y_test, y_pred, alpha=0.5)
plt.plot([min(y_test), max(y_test)], [min(y_test), max(y_test)], linestyle='--', color='red')
plt.xlabel('Actual')
plt.ylabel('Predicted')
plt.title('Linear Regression: with outliers')

# Mark RMSE on the plot
plt.text(min(y_test), max(y_pred), f'RMSE = {rmse:.2f}', fontsize=12, verticalalignment='bottom')
plt.show()
```